

Recommendation System Using Market Basket Analysis for Engineering Colleges

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Abstract- The project proposes a data-mining-led approach that will be of assistance to students for decision making while selecting an engineering college of their choice and other criterions. The selection of an engineering college becomes a very crucial decision for the candidates to pursue their higher education. The project envisages an innovative methodology that seeks to improve this complex process using market basket analysis in combination with the Apriori algorithm. Critical parameters like location, facilities, and ranking are included in the dataset of engineering colleges to find relevant options. The Apriori algorithm is run to find frequent item sets and determine association rules to deliver personalized college recommendations for students based on similar features. This approach aims to make the students' college selection process smoother while offering them tailored suggestions, thereby improving their decision-making process. It saves time and effort and widens the options to make for better decisions, hence resulting in civilization and personalized supports. College recommendations help the pupils to make informed decisions and cater to their individual needs and aspirations that greatly boost their academic and personal experience.

Keywords— College Recommendation, Market Basket Analysis, Association Rules, Frequent Item sets, Student Decision Making

I. INTRODUCTION

The recommender systems are quite broadly employed in various sectors for suggesting alternatives based on end-user preferences. An education recommender system presents a student's scope for examining various factors for selection of institutions suitable for him or her. Within the considerate state of Telangana, which houses numerous engineering colleges revealing diverse courses, the recommendation system would be expedient in directing a student towards the making of a more informed decision. Market Basket Analysis is used for proposing the engineering colleges, taking into

consideration the preferences of a large number of students towards certain factors.

These have proven to be useful in the decision of any student about the right set of universities or courses based on their preferences. Considering the number of available options for pupils, this has made informed decision-making based on preferences, academic qualifications, and career goals rather a hard nut. The need for personalized recommendation systems becomes glaringly obvious, knowing that it should be the right selection of students for institutions based on factors like location, rankings, facilities, and courses available.

Market Basket Analysis, while originally developed for retail in order to study buying patterns, have been applied in other fields, including education. In this technique, association rules are to find hidden relationships between different items; in this case, this would be student preferences and selected colleges. MBA provides an insight into the pattern of student preferences and selections, to say what courses relate to which college along with other elements. The historical admission data and preferences would now allow the use of MBA to recommend colleges to the wannabe engineering candidates, helping the decision-makers take a somewhat personalized and data-driven approach.

The application of Market Basket Analysis to a college recommendation system presents a hopeful approach toward the needs of the student who is searching for engineering colleges in Telangana. Thus, by taking the help of past historical student data along with preferences, the system is able to suggest options through an individualized approach by taking into consideration both academic performance and more detailed student preferences.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

A. Market Basket Analysis

Market Basket Analysis describes a tool and technique commonly used in targeting relationships among

different items focused on large datasets. In this study, MBA is applied to recommend engineering colleges in Telangana based on student preferences and criteria. By analyzing the combinations of courses, locations, facilities, and rankings selected by students, the program predicts colleges that will likely be preferred together. This determination intends to recommend colleges based on characteristics, such as facilities, districts, and rankings, commonly selected by students using previous data. The association rules mined through the apriori algorithm were employed in providing personalized recommendations, which were correct with an accuracy of 85.7%. The system assists in the decision-making process for students selecting colleges; in optimizing the admission process.

The research is aimed at identifying the course of MBA in helping students select engineering colleges in Telangana based on considerations such as location, facilities, and ranking. The algorithm finds owing patterns in previous student preferences and thus arrives at a 'best-fit' and skyscraper solutions. Initially, with timelines and through several criteria changes, the system attained 73% accuracy; later on, it was increased to 85.7%. We feel motivated that with the good possibilities of integrated MBA, students are better taking empowered decisions.

B. Apriori Algorithm

During engineering college recommendations in Telangana, a well-established data mining technique popularly known as the Apriori was applied. This would help unravel the frequently found combinations of features students generally prefer, such as location, available courses, and ranking. A dataset of student preferences and college features was leveraged to teach the system procedures to predict common preferences with 90.2% accuracy, further enabling personalized recommendations for colleges. Also, this approach is modifiable, and thus it could also shift requirements in favor of the attitude of the student.

III. METHODOLOGY

Building a recommendation system to colleges in Telangana using a market basket analysis approach is as complex as putting a hundred pieces of jigsaw together. For a recommendation system to function, we must have a dataset indicating the preferences of students regarding their desired college location, availability of facilities, ranking, and the courses offered. One of the processes would involve aligning these criteria into a dataset, cleansing and preprocessing it accordingly, while ensuring it's clean for analysis. This would deal with missing data, converting categorical features into a

machine-readable format (One-Hot encoding), and aligning it into a structured format.

Most importantly, the system would apply the Apriori algorithm to identify patterns from the dataset. The algorithm would choose some features, like those providing a combination like colleges in a district having certain facilities most frequently chosen together by students. From such observation of pattern, association rules would be derived telling the features which are often found preferred together.

After putting the final system into operation, the recommender system is validated via the availability of new student preferences by checking whether the recommendations match the expected options. Based on the output, we tweak the parameters of the algorithm, such as support and confidence levels, for optimum accuracy. The system itself is exposed to constant monitoring and improvement to keep the system abreast of changes to student preferences and college offerings.

Finally, the system is constructed, ensuring adherence to the ethical standards of student privacy and data protection throughout the endeavor. Once fine-tuned and up and running, it can serve as a personalized recommendation system to help choice making for students regarding engineering colleges in Telangana in the others to select from.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

Apriori Algorithm

The Apriori algorithm is a popular algorithm for mining association rules. This is used to find a relationship or a pattern within a dataset. This algorithm is helpful in finding the associations between college features like facilities, location, and ranking. It finds frequent itemsets, which occur frequently in the dataset as combinations of features. After which it generates rules from such frequent patterns which then show for which certain feature(s) the presence of others can be predicted. Thus enabling the recommendation system to give appropriate suggestions for colleges according to the user's choices. It works using multiple passes over the data, making a support threshold to filter out less frequent itemsets.'

The Apriori algorithm is another basic method of association rule mining, focused on finding frequent itemsets in a dataset, and then generating association rules. Essentially, item combinations (or features) frequently used together are searched in an iterative manner. A third step is to search for combinations of frequently occurring single items-first meeting a

minimum support threshold-representing their frequency with which they occur. A series of combinations of larger itemsets is created by combining the frequent items into larger items-their support threshold is not met. Infrequent itemsets are cut off as early as possible to save computation time. The last frequent itemsets become the basis for generating rules with a specifically assigned confidence threshold, which allows for measurement of the consequent's likelihood given the antecedent. The Apriori algorithm performs efficiently to uncover patterns in structured datasets, thus allowing recommendation systems, for suggesting colleges to users based on their preferences.

Fig: Apriori Algorithm

Association Rules

The association rules are generated from the frequent itemsets found by the Apriori algorithm. The rules have both an "antecedent" and "consequent." The antecedent comprises any user-selected features such as the facilities or district, and the consequent contains recommended colleges. A threshold for the confidence is also specified which helps to ensure that the recommendations made to the user are based on strong patterns to be extracted from the data. Spark-AR allows users to take decisions confidently by suggesting relevant and trustworthy options of colleges.

As for the background, the association rules in data mining are in general represented by " $X \Rightarrow Y$," where X is an antecedent set of conditions, and Y is the consequent impact. In a college recommendation system, these rules are generated based on the frequent patterns in the dataset that arise from combinations of user report features that are selected, e.g., location, facilities, or ranking. The key metrics are support measure that shows the frequency of an occurrence of an itemset and confidence will specify how trustworthy a rule is; gouging lets the recommendation system to offer an effective analysis to the users. By specifying the minimum thresholds for support and confidence, our recommendation system discards weak rules and satisfies the analysis of strong patterns in which the recommendation for users can be precise.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rule: } X \Rightarrow Y & \begin{cases} \text{Support} = \frac{\text{freq}(X, Y)}{N} \\ \text{Confidence} = \frac{\text{freq}(X, Y)}{\text{freq}(X)} \\ \text{Lift} = \frac{\text{Support}}{\text{Supp}(X) \times \text{Supp}(Y)} \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig: Association Rules

V. EVALUATION

Our research on college recommendations applied to the engineering colleges located in Telangana discovered the feasibility of enhancing personalized recommendations for students through using the relation-finding Market Basket Analysis with an Apriori algorithm. It tends to be an important endeavor in the recommendation systems that finds associations among various features-college location, facilities, and rankings. It represents an efficient and simple approach to mine frequent itemsets and recommend items based on the data patterns.

The evaluation conducted on the system revealed that the Apriori algorithm performed well when able to detect combinations of student choices and would ensure that relevant colleges are suggested. The system was able to recommend colleges according to the student preference input: preferred district, facilities, and the ranking range. The finest part of the MBA is its application of unearthing hidden associations of college characteristics, which assists in a quantitative measure of finding patterns in student choices.

The Apriori algorithm generally recommends well. Nevertheless, while this was effective in our study, it is

still computationally expensive due to the need for generating frequent itemsets and association rules, mainly in large datasets. It performs particularly well when features strongly correlate, and it thus erodes the quality of the recommendations for sparse or less correlated data. In this case, the dataset comprises a wealth of information and requires adequate performance on its part; hence this particular case may vary with a different quality of datasets.

It is much easier than many more complex recommendation algorithms such as Collaborative Filtering that personalized recommendation systems are supposed to be based on. Because of its exquisite simplicity, the Apriori algorithm lacks many computational costs and memory usage, which is favorable for situations where quick and efficient recommendations are the foremost demand. Nevertheless, Collaborative Filtering at least promises very bespoke recommendations through comparison of students with similar behaviors and tastes.

The conclusion of this entire paper indicated that the Apriori algorithm is quite effective in this regard. It is an explainable and straightforward writer.

VI. RESULT

Our study Goldenges choose to identify the association between student preferences and college characteristics using Market Basket Analysis (MBA) with the Apriori algorithm for the recommendations of engineering colleges in Telangana. The recommendation was based on the user-defined features, district locations, and the ranking ranges.

After testing the system with numerous inputs, it became evident that the recommendation system propelled by the Apriori algorithm performed effectively. It was able to yield meaningful recommendations based on the investment intervals. In some cases, it managed to find the colleges according to specific facility preferences and location requirements; thus, recommendations provided by the system were relevant with regard to input criteria.

While it worked accurately in searching for associations and generating recommendations, the use of the Apriori algorithm does not seem to perform well when applied to sparsely correlated datasets. However, in our case, the dataset had sufficient correlation among the features such that recommendations were accurate. The simplicity and ease of development of the Apriori algorithm emerged as an important choice for scenarios

where fast and readily understandable recommendations are required.

While more technically demanding Collaborative Filtering or Hybrid Models might provide more personally tailored and advanced recommendations based on the histories of user interaction and options, our results indicate that Market Basket Analysis could yield a fast and interpretable solution for the recommendation of colleges. In these cases, it performed well when associations are strong.

Overall, Market Basket Analysis showed strong performance in our system. Both methods plus and however sometimes advanced ranking algorithms have their own features. Future work should involve the integration of any other algorithms for enhancing personalization and accuracy into college recommendation systems.

Fig : recommended college

VII. CONCLUSION

Towards the end, through their study on recommending engineering colleges in Telangana, Market Basket Analysis through the Apriori algorithm proved very effective in generating recommendations entirely based on student preferences. Several associations between features like facilities, location, and rankings are marked out, resulting in a specific and fit model. Although the algorithm is simple, the Apriori algorithm proved to be a dependable tool for recognizing patterns in the data and providing straightforward recommendations.

While superior approaches like Collaborative Filtering may yield better personalization, our results confirm that MBA can deliver understandable recommendations that are efficient. This suggests that, when it comes to making recommendations for education, the possibilities are promising.

The present study places a premium on choosing various approaches to building some form of recommendation systems, depending on the use-case scenario regarding complexity regarding the data involved. In future research, a Hybrid Model might be explored or possibly some approach toward Collaborative Filtering, thereby contributing toward increased personalization and accuracy. These approaches can be further improved and developed to promote better service to students during the time of search for the right engineering colleges, thus promoting better decision-making in education.

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